

COVID-19 INFLUENCE ON WATER- ENERGY-FOOD NEXUS OF ISRAEL AND EXPERIENCE FOR EUROPEAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract: *The virus of COVID-19 paralyzed the whole world and got populations of most of the countries of the world into serious quarantine and the world economy into deep crisis. However, epidemiology experts often disagree and claim that the climate crisis will continue and bring about more pandemic and other emergencies in the next decades. Israeli experts are sure that ecology changes will provoke more diseases, especially in places where they were not common before. In this paper, the author tries to find out what is special about Israeli policy recommendations in water, ecology, energy and food in Israel during the corona crisis.*

Key words: *Water-Energy-Food, COVID-19, crisis, Israeli policy, international experience.*

ВЛИЯНИЕ КОВИД-19 НА СИСТЕМУ ВОДА-ЭНЕРГИЯ-ПИТАНИЕ В ИЗРАИЛЕ И ОПЫТ ДЛЯ СТРАН ЕВРОПЫ

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Аннотация: *Вирус КОВИД-19 парализовал весь мир и отправил населения многих стран мира в карантин, вызвав сильнейший экономический кризис. Вместе с тем, эксперты-эпидемиологи часто утверждают, что климатический кризис гораздо более серьёзен и в будущем принесёт ещё эпидемии и катастрофы. Израильские эксперты уверены в том, что изменения в экологии повысит заболеваемость, охватив новые регионы. В данной работе, автор пытается выяснить что характеризует Израильскую политику в вопросах воды, экологии, энергии и продуктов питания во время коронавирусного кризиса.*

Ключевые слова: *Вода-Энергия-Питание, КОВИД-19, кризис, израильская политика, международный опыт.*

Introduction

The virus of COVID-19 paralyzed the whole world and got populations of most of the countries of the world into serious quarantine and the world economy into deep crisis. This crisis is so wide, traumatic and special so that all of us hope it is a one-time event. However, epidemiology experts often disagree and claim that the climate crisis will continue and bring about more pandemic and other emergencies in the next decades (Kabir [5]). Prof. Davidovitz from Israel [5] is sure that ecology changes will provoke more diseases, especially in places where they were not common before. In this paper, the authors try to find out what is special about policy recommendations in water, ecology, energy and food in Israel during the corona crisis from March 2020 till the end of 2020.

Water and electricity

In 2020, due to the pandemic, many companies and governmental institutions had to work distantly. Teleworking (telecommuting) is one of the policy tools that can alter road travel demand, by allowing employees to avoid travelling in peak hours and in high demand areas. Levi et.al. [6] examined the subject of implementing this policy in Israel in general, and in light of the COVID-19 pandemic effects in particular. Teleworking, as they suggest, has a great potential for economic and social benefits, such as saving negative externalities of transportation, increasing productivity, strengthening the periphery areas, reducing gender inequality and making the labor market accessible to underprivileged populations.

Naturally, working from home increase domestic use of water and electricity. According to Israeli Water Authority, the amount of water for domestic use- including households, commerce and industry- was in March 2020 about 5% higher than a year ago. Assuming that the population grew up about 8.1%, in the whole national domestic use perspective, the real growth in water consumption was about 2.3% per capita for domestic use including housekeeping, commerce and industry. Since commerce and industry were partially closed and their consumption must have been reduced, the only explanation is that households consumed more water during 2020 [9]. The untreated wastewater usage grew up in about 5%. There is a high variance between different regions' water corporation reports: the Motzkin water Corporation reported increase in 30% of water consumption in 2020, whereas the south Eilat Corporation reported a 20% decrease in comparison between March of 2020 and March of 2019. This is reasonable since Eilat is a tourism based city. In the region of Jerusalem, no change of water consumption was observed. Some of changes are attributed to changes in different production

sectors- for example, tourism almost completely stopped during 2020. In March-November of 2020 there was an increase of 4.5% in domestic water consumption, compared to the same period of 2019 [10].

Agriculture sector, on the contrary, was developed and needed more investment and consideration at the time of pandemic. More water is needed for the agriculture, and this trend will probably continue after the pandemic [9]. Palatnik [7] points out the scarcity of water in Israel due to climate changes and population growth. These phenomena got even more severe during the pandemic.

Domestic usage of electricity grew up in about 7.6%, according to summary data of the company of electricity management of Israel [4]. At the same time, general consumption of electricity did not change at all [4]. The company of electricity management of Israel claims there are two reasons for that: the first is a set of lockdowns closures that were imposed on the Israeli public since the pandemic began. The second one is the change of climate and heat waves that stroke the country in the year of 2020 – such powerful ones that need a use of conditioners at seasons when it is usually not necessary. As a result, electricity is used intensely.

The electricity company, the main supplier of electricity for private domestic consumers, published its incomes, allowing to evaluate how the domestic usage of electricity changes in 2020 compared to 2019 [4]. If we treat the months separately, the highest increase in domestic electricity use was in September of 2020 (increase of 13% related to 2019), in February (8.5% more than in 2019), and October (increase of 6%). On the contrary, decrease in electricity use was registered in June (10%), April (9%) and March (5%).

The following figure presents average Israeli electricity production per hour for February-April of 2018- 2020 [2]. The period of March is divided into 2 sub-periods: the first one (1.03-14.03) before the schools were closed, and the second one (15.03- 31.03) when they were closed by the government decision. In 2019, there was an increase in average electricity production per hour. In March till April of 2020, the lockdown period, there was a decrease, in comparison to the previous year.

Figure 1. Electricity consumption per year. Source: Ben Hamo et.al., 2020 [2]

As mentioned earlier, the general consumption of Israeli electricity in 2020 almost didn't change. It means that in general it is a decrease: if the general population grew up in about 2%, and the electricity use increased in only 0.2%. In a "usual" year it could be expected the electricity consumption would grow up, however in 2020 it decreased, especially on the account of public trade and industry sectors, which balanced an increase in consumption in private sector and natural population growth [4].

The following figure presents percentage changes in electricity consumption from 2019 to 2020 by sectors:

Figure 2. Percentage of change in Israeli electricity consumption from 2019 to 2020 by sectors. Source: Fisher (2021) [3]

The more the pandemic kept spreading, the more intense was general decrease in electricity use in Israel. Since many institutions in industry, trades and education sector were closed and employees worked from home, were on vacation or fired, the general consumption of electricity in these sectors decreased, which balanced the increase of domestic use.

Food

Since the Covid-19 is spreading rapidly all the over the world and still there are no tools to stop it immediately, many countries keep emergency status. The ports get closed, some exports are reduced, airplanes are grounded and food markets are also closed, so that each country has to solve its own food problems within its own boundaries [1].

If Israel aims to solve its food problems alone, Atar [1] claims it will encounter a local catastrophe as a result of neglecting of agriculture market for years. Nine millions of people may find themselves without a food, and panic will prevail [5]. There are opinions that counting on import is like a suicide in the current reality [1]. Even if these pessimistic prognoses are not likely to materialize, the authors think attention should be paid to the local agriculture, its current status and possible future development directions.

The United Nations organization evaluates in its documents dedicated to nutrition and food issues that the Covid-19 crisis is going to double a number of people who suffer from hunger and lack of some foods on a global level (Promotion of food safety for the whole population at the period of Corona [8]). Israel, like many other countries in the world, strives to allow employment and routine, and to keep up with existing food supplying systems, safe food supply chains and special food supply programs, like supply of meals at schools. Much more citizens need help now as a result of quarantines, lockdowns and unemployment, altogether with logistic changes in food distributions, leaving families without a food safety.

Agriculture sector lost foods as a result of markets' closures and decrease in consumptions of institutions, restaurants, exports. This sector was damaged both on national and international levels (Promotion of food safety for the whole population at the period of Corona, 2020)..

Food national safety is defined as a variety of foods at the base of national nutrition recommendations, available for the whole population [8]. In order to supply food safety in this tough emergency period, the Israeli Ministry of Health claims the following three steps are required:

1. Saving life and earnings by concentrating on the most vulnerable populations: keeping food for humanitarian and critical needs;

- The diseased and hospital patients: supplying food for medical (treatment) purposes for patients who need special foods during their hospitalization and treatment at home;

- The patients of special “Corona hotels” should be taken care of properly, including their nutrition.

2. Strengthening social defense systems for healthy foods: for example, to supply cash and coupons to purchase or distribute foods, to supply diverse, healthy and balanced food to populations at risk like elderly, unemployed and minorities.

3. Intensive investment of development of sustainable future: building up sustainable and environment-friendly food chains, encouraging healthy and safe choice of nutrition. Healthy and cheap food basket may be achieved by competition or prices’ inspection.

Summary

This study aims to evaluate the Covid-19 crisis impacts and consequences over Israeli WEF nexus answer the question how the vaccination will succeed in getting Israel back to normal, out of the economic crisis, and to better situation in the WEF- water, ecology and food domains over time.

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